

RECRUITMENT, TRAINING, POSITION ARRANGEMENT, ASSESSMENT AND INCENTIVE FACTORS INFLUENCING VOLUNTEER MANAGEMENT MODEL OF ZHENGKAI INTERNATIONAL MARATHON IN CHINA

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Abstract

In recent years, marathon has developed rapidly in China, and marathon volunteers have been given a new mission as an important part of the national fitness volunteer service. The objective of this research were: 1) To study the current situation and affecting factors of Zhengkai International Marathon volunteer management in China. 2) To analyze factors positive effect the volunteer management model for the Zhengkai International Marathon in China. 3) To examine and confirm the volunteer management model of Zhengkai International Marathon in China. This research employed a mixed research methodology combining qualitative and quantitative. For the qualitative research part, in-depth interviews are conducted with 21 insiders, including leaders of the competent departments of Zhengkai International Marathon, experts in sports event management and event volunteer managers. In the quantitative research part, the sample consisted of 440 volunteers who participated in Zhengkai International Marathon in 2023 and were sampled proportioned according to different post Settings. Data were obtained through questionnaire survey. Amos software were used to conduct quantitative establish structural equation model (SEM). Another qualitative analysis was conducted through a 15-person focus group consisting of road running experts of the Athletics Association, leaders of the Zheng Kai International Marathon, and relevant race point leaders to verify and discuss the model. The research findings revealed that: 1) China Zhengkai International Marathon has developed rapidly and has its own characteristics, but there is still room for improvement in volunteer organization and management. 2) Volunteer recruitment, training, post arrangement, assessment and incentive positive affect the volunteer management model of Zheng Kai Marathon. Volunteer satisfaction played a mediating role, all fitting parameters of the model are within the acceptable range, and all hypotheses are valid. 3) Through experts the focus group discussion, the volunteer management model of Zhengkai International Marathon has been examined and confirmed, and the volunteer management model of Zhengkai International Marathon can be promoted and applied. The research results can directly provide reference for marathon volunteer management organizations in China, and enrich the theoretical research of marathon volunteer human resource management practice.

Keywords: Volunteer Management Model / Factors Influencing / Zhengkai International Marathon.

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the Central Committee of the Communist Party of China and The State Council promulgated the Outline of Healthy China 2030 Plan (2016), the implementation of the national fitness strategy has accelerated in China. On June 24, 2019, The State Council issued the "Healthy China Action Organization Implementation Evaluation Plan", emphasizing that people's health is a sign of a rich and strong country, and requiring a wide range of national fitness activities across the country. With the extensive development of the event, more and more marathon members participate in the event, which puts forward higher requirements for marathon services. The "Measures for the Management of Sports Events (2022)" issued by the General Administration of Sport of the State put forward basic requirements for volunteers in sports events. The organization and management of volunteers is a very important link for the smooth development of sports events, so the management mode related to volunteers is particularly important. China Zhengkai International Marathon is a permanent large-scale international sports event in Henan Province and one of the most popular marathons in China. The number of volunteers required for each session is about 5,000, and good volunteer management and operation play an important role in the success of the event. The study of the volunteer management mode of China Zhengkai International Marathon not only has practical guiding significance for the continuous improvement and optimization of the event, but also is an inevitable requirement for implementing the national fitness strategy and building a sports power, and has a positive impact on the academic research in the field of volunteer management and the promotion of social welfare undertakings.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Characteristics and Attributes of Marathon Event Service Management

The international definition of the identity of volunteers mainly includes the following points: voluntary, free, structural and benefit to others. Sports volunteers are people who voluntarily contribute their time, energy and wisdom to promote the development of human sports cause and provide services for sports cause without material reward. The characteristics of volunteers in sports events can be summarized from the following aspects: From the perspective of participation time, service time is concentrated and phased. From the perspective of organization and management, large-scale sports events are generally sponsored by the government, hosted by institutions, universities or associations, organized and planned carefully, the assignment of tasks is clear, and each performs its own duties. From the perspective of participants, the background of volunteers is diversified and the personal quality level is hierarchical, but the volunteers are mainly college students, supplemented by young people, their behavior is random, and their participation motivation is diverse. From the perspective of the impact of sports volunteer service, it can improve social and economic benefits, promote the normal operation of sports events, and also show the cultural connotation of a city and a country. In general, we can believe that current scholars have different views on marathon volunteer service management, but no consensus has been reached. There are different attributes, and these characteristics are mainly divided by category attributes.

2.2 Study on the Influencing Factors of Marathon Volunteer Management

Tuo (2021, p.173-176) Study on volunteer organization and management of 2020 Guangzhou Marathon. Taking Guangzhou Marathon 2020 as a case, this paper analyzes the current situation of the organization and management of volunteers in this marathon from six perspectives: recruitment management, training management, allocation management, incentive management, supervision and evaluation management, and discharge management, and analyzes the existing problems.

American scholar Joan E. Pynes(2002,p.36), Human Resource Management in public and non-profit organizations, The book is a great inspiration for the human resource management of members of public and non-profit organizations, social workers and volunteers, and analyzes the process of volunteer recruitment, selection, training, evaluation and management in detail.

Tang (2020, p.182-183) Research on the status quo and innovation of volunteer service management in large-scale sports events. This paper investigated the volunteer service management of Xuzhou International Marathon, from the recruitment, post setting, training, security and incentive measures of volunteers, so as to explore the current situation and existing problems of volunteer service management of large-scale sports events, and then put forward suggestions and countermeasures. Based on relevant research results, this study selected volunteer recruitment, training, position arrangement, assessment and Incentive as the influencing factors for volunteer management of China Zhengkai International Marathon.

2.3 Study on the Effect of Volunteer Management Model

Cheng (2017, p.35) this paper explores the management mode of museum volunteers in China from the perspective of participation motivation. With reference to the Self-Determination Theory (SDT), this paper puts forward the corresponding scientific management concept, hoping to create a healthy environment for the external development of museums and volunteers, and build a mechanism conducive to benign interaction between the two. Under the joint action of internal and external, by analyzing the participation motivation of the core volunteers of the museum, we can improve the management of museum volunteers, strengthen the participation motivation of volunteers, and improve the work enthusiasm and stability of volunteers.

Xue (2020, p.140-141) How to improve the service efficiency of volunteers in museums. The article points out that expanding recruitment sources, enriching post types, refining training and assessment standards, strict volunteer management system, and improving volunteer welfare security are effective ways to satisfy volunteer satisfaction and improve service efficiency. Xin (2023, p.808) Analysis of influencing factors and security needs of volunteer service efficiency. It is pointed out that establishing a perfect social security mechanism for volunteer service, strengthening the training of volunteers' first-aid skills, and equipping volunteers with necessary first-aid equipment and supplies are the necessary ways to encourage the extensive participation of first-aid volunteers, improve the efficiency of first-aid volunteer service, and promote the construction and development of first-aid community

system. The volunteer management model is of great significance to improve the ability and work effectiveness of volunteers and ensure the smooth and orderly progress of activities through the recruitment, training, position arrangement, assessment and incentive of volunteers and on the basis of volunteer satisfaction.

2.4 Research Framework

In this study, the recruitment, training, post arrangement and assessment incentive of marathon volunteers were taken as independent variables, the satisfaction of volunteers as intermediary variable, and volunteer management model as dependent variable. Based on literature review and research purpose, the model of influencing factors of volunteer management of Zheng Kai International Marathon was constructed. Figure 1 shows a schematic of this model.

Figure 1: The Model of Influencing Factors of Volunteer Management of Zheng Kai International Marathon

Based on the relationship among the model of volunteer recruitment, training, post arrangement, Assessment incentive influencing factors of volunteer management in China Zhengkai International Marathon, the research hypothesis is proposed:

H1: The marathon volunteer recruitment factors positively affect the volunteer management model of Zhengkai International Marathon in China;

- H2: The marathon volunteer training factors positively affect the volunteer management model of Zhengkai International Marathon in China;
- H3: The position arrangement of marathon volunteers' factors positively affect the volunteer management model of Zhengkai International Marathon in China;
- H4: The assessment and Incentive of marathon volunteers' factors positively affect the volunteer management model of Zhengkai International Marathon in China;
- H5: The marathon volunteer recruitment factors positively affect the volunteer satisfaction;
- H6: The marathon volunteer training factors positively affect the volunteer satisfaction;
- H7: The position arrangement of marathon volunteers' factors positively affect the volunteer satisfaction;
- H8: The assessment and Incentive of marathon volunteers' factors positively affect the volunteer satisfaction;
- H9: Volunteer satisfaction positively affects the volunteer management model of Zhengkai International Marathon in China;
- H10: Volunteer satisfaction plays an intermediary role factors positively affect between volunteer recruitment and volunteer management model of Zhengkai International Marathon in China;
- H11: Volunteer satisfaction plays an intermediary role factors positively affect between volunteer training and volunteer management model of Zhengkai International Marathon in China;
- H12: Volunteer satisfaction plays an intermediary role factors positively affect between volunteer position arrangement and volunteer management model of Zhengkai International Marathon in China;
- H13: Volunteer satisfaction plays an intermediary role factors positively affect between volunteer assessment and Incentive and volunteer management model of Zhengkai International Marathon in China.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

A mixed method of qualitative and quantitative analysis was used in the study. Firstly, through literature analysis and in-depth interviews with 21 relevant personnel, the status quo and influencing factors of volunteer management of Zheng Kai International Marathon were summarized. Secondly, the questionnaire of influencing factors of the development of marathon volunteer service management was designed, and the reliability and validity of IOC were tested with a small sample of 30 people. 500 formal questionnaires were issued, 440 valid samples were collected, and structural equation models were established through quantitative confirmatory factor analysis. Finally, a focus group of 15 people was formed for discussion and qualitative analysis to verify the effectiveness and accuracy of Zheng International Horse Race volunteer management model.

4. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Qualitative Analysis

Through literature analysis and interviews with leaders of the National marathon authorities, sports management experts and volunteer managers, this paper summarizes the influencing factors of volunteer management, and reviews the current situation of marathon volunteer management from the aspects of volunteer recruitment, training, post arrangement and incentive system.

In general, China Zhengkai International Marathon has developed rapidly and has its own unique characteristics, and there is still room for improvement in volunteer organization and management. Respondents said that in order to better promote volunteer management, more efforts should be made to assess volunteers, put people first, improve volunteers' personal satisfaction, improve work efficiency, and promote the smooth progress of competitions and the sustainable development of volunteer services.

4.2 Quantitative Research, Data Analysis

4.2.1 Descriptive Analysis

Table 1: Basic Demographic Characteristics

Name	Options	Frequency □	Percentage (%)	Cumulative percentage (%) □
Age	Under 20 years old	338	76.82	76.82
	21-30 years old	80	18.18	95.00
	31-40 years old	22	5.00	100.00
Gender	Male	213	48.41	48.41
	Female	227	51.59	100.00
Education Background	Junior college	91	20.68	20.68
	Undergraduate course	327	74.32	95.00
	Postgraduate	22	5.00	100.00
occupation	Students	412	93.64	93.64
	clerk	28	6.36	100.00
Registration method	Online individual registration	164	37.27	37.27
	Online group registration	125	28.41	65.68
	Recruitment on-site registration	25	5.68	71.36
	Other	126	28.64	100.00

As can be seen from the above table, most of the samples are "under 20 years old", with a total of 338.0, accounting for 76.82%. More than 50% of the sample chose "male". A further 48.41% of the sample was female.

In terms of academic qualifications, the proportion of "undergraduate" is the highest 74.32%. 93.64% of the occupations in the sample were students. From the perspective of registration distribution, most of the samples were "online individual registration", with a total of 164.0, accounting for 37.27%.

4.2.2 Reliability and Validity Test of Scale

Table 2: Reliability test summary of each scale

Scale	Number of entries	Cronbach α coefficient
Volunteer recruitment	16	0.986
Volunteer training	16	0.990
Volunteer position arrangement	16	0.988
Volunteer assessment and incentive	16	0.988
Volunteer satisfaction	12	0.990
Volunteer management model	12	0.989

As can be seen from the above table, the reliability test of the 6 scales has passed, and all items should be retained.

Table 3: Factor analysis and discrimination of each scale

Scale	KMO value	Bartlett's P value
Volunteer recruitment	0.862	0.000
Volunteer training	0.768	0.000
Volunteer position arrangement	0.726	0.000
Volunteer assessment and incentive	0.793	0.000
Volunteer satisfaction	0.803	0.000
Volunteer management model	0.721	0.000

It can be seen from the table that the KMO coefficients of the 6 scales are all greater than 0.7, and the Bartlett's P values are all less than 0.001, indicating that the 6 scales are suitable for factor analysis.

4.2.3 Structural Equation Model

Figure 2: Marathon Volunteer Management Structural Equation Model

Table 4: Structural equation model fitting index

χ^2/DF	GFI	TLI	CFI	RMSEA	RMR
2.317	0.917	0.907	0.932	0.032	0.021

Table 5: Model structure path coefficient test

Path			Nonnormalized coefficient	S.E.	C.R.	P	Standardization coefficient
MYD	<---	ZYZZM	0.067	0.019	3.501	***	0.092
MYD	<---	GWAP	0.501	0.033	15.352	***	0.732
MYD	<---	ZYZPX	0.030	0.011	2.609	0.009	0.043
MYD	<---	PJL	0.358	0.026	13.590	***	0.507
GLMX	<---	MYD	0.715	0.069	10.364	***	0.794
GLMX	<---	GWAP	0.072	0.032	2.265	0.024	0.117
GLMX	<---	ZYZZM	0.100	0.015	6.464	***	0.153
GLMX	<---	ZYZPX	-0.002	0.008	-0.180	0.857	-0.002
GLMX	<---	PJL	0.074	0.025	2.935	0.003	0.116

Combined with the results of the figure above and the table, it can be seen that the overall path coefficient of the marathon volunteer management model is significant. The path coefficients among volunteer recruitment (GZYZM), volunteer training (GYZPX), volunteer position arrangement (GWAP), volunteer evaluation motivation and retention (PJL), volunteer satisfaction (MYD) and volunteer management model (GLMX) were significant ($P < 0.01$).

The research hypotheses are valid, and the value of the convergence coefficient CR is within the standard range. In addition, we tested the fitting parameters of the model, and the results showed that the chi-square value was 2.317, P value < 0.001 , GFI=0.917, CFI=0.932, TLI=0.907, RMSEA=0.032, RMR=0.021, and the reference estimates were all within the standard range. It shows that the marathon volunteer service management mode can be popularized and used, and has good effectiveness.

4.3 Qualitative Analysis

A focus group was set up through the target population, and the sample selection took into account diversity in age, gender, participation, and loyalty. The validation process of the focus group includes discussion of the model, answers to questions, and recommendations. To verify the mediating role of satisfaction among volunteer recruitment, training, post arrangement, assessment incentive and work efficiency. The focus group agreed on the degree of fit between the path coefficients and the final model variables that the model could be generalized.

5. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

5.1 Conclusion

5.1.1 Through literature analysis and in-depth interviews, the influencing factors of volunteer management of China Zhengkai International Marathon include volunteer recruitment, training, post arrangement, assessment and incentive.

China Zhengkai International Marathon has developed rapidly and has its own unique characteristics, and there is still room for improvement in volunteer organization and management.

5.1.2 Through the descriptive analysis of the basic information, the evaluation of each observation item is generally consistent, and there are no outliers. The relevant hypothesis is verified: marathon volunteer recruitment, volunteer training, volunteer position arrangement, volunteer assessment and incentive have a positive impact on the volunteer management model; Marathon volunteer recruitment, volunteer training, volunteer post arrangement, volunteer assessment and incentive have a positive impact on volunteer satisfaction; Volunteer satisfaction has a positive impact on volunteer management model; Volunteer satisfaction is an intermediary factor that affects marathon volunteer recruitment, volunteer training, volunteer position arrangement, volunteer assessment and incentive, and volunteer management mode.

The structural equation model of volunteer management in Zheng International Marathon is established. The reliability test shows that the fitting degree of the model meets the standard.

5.1.3 Through the focus group discussion, the structural equation model has good reliability and effectiveness, all fitting parameters of the model are within the acceptable range, and the constructed model is reasonable. In this study, the volunteer management service model of China Zhengkai International Marathon can be promoted and applied.

5.2 Discussion

5.2.1 The marathon volunteer recruitment factors positively affect volunteer management model

In the path analysis of volunteer recruitment to volunteer management model, there is a nonstandardized coefficient of 0.864, a standardized coefficient of 0.904, a highly significant P-value (***), and a critical ratio (C.R.) of 27.867. The results show that volunteer recruitment has a significant positive effect on volunteer management model.

Recruitment is the first step of human resource management, but also a crucial part. Yu (2023) pointed out that in order to improve the quality of talent recruitment, the source of high-quality talents lays a high-quality talent foundation for the development of enterprises and improves work efficiency.

5.2.2 The marathon volunteer training factors positively affect volunteer management model

The non-normalized coefficient was 0.944, the highly significant P-value (***), and the critical ratio (C.R.) was 28.699. The standardized coefficient of 0.934 indicates that volunteer training has a significant positive impact on volunteer management model.

Ding (2008) proposed that good pre-job training is conducive to improving work efficiency. Huang (2019) pointed out that university management training has a certain impact on improving work efficiency.

5.2.3 The position arrangement of marathon volunteers' factors positively affect the volunteer management model

The study found that the effect of volunteer position arrangement on volunteer management model, the non-normalized coefficient was 0.936, with a highly significant P-value (***), C.R.

Is 29.075, the standardization coefficient is 0.948. This indicates that volunteer position arrangement has a significant positive effect on volunteer management model. Consistent with the following related research views: Zhang (2018) pointed out that reasonable post Settings can optimize the organizational structure and effectively improve the work efficiency and management level of public institutions.

Zhang (2020) when arranging the specific work of volunteers, the expertise of volunteers should be considered first, and volunteers should be assigned to corresponding posts to improve their work efficiency.

5.2.4 The assessment and Incentive of marathon volunteers' factors positively affect volunteer management model

It is found that the non-standardized coefficient is 0.914, the P-value (***) is significant, the standard error (S.E.) is 0.034, the critical ratio (C.R.) is 27.121, and the standardized coefficient is 0.950. This indicates that the volunteer assessment incentive has a significant positive impact on volunteer management model.

The relevant views are verified. Wang (2009) the starting point of motivation is to meet various needs of incentive objects, which ultimately affects work efficiency. Huang (2018) pointed out that factors such as volunteers' incentive content, incentive method, reward and punishment system are the core components of incentive mechanism, which affect volunteers' work efficiency and the success or failure of competition.

5.2.5 The marathon volunteer recruitment factors positively affect the volunteer satisfaction

In the test of structured path coefficient between volunteer recruitment and satisfaction, the non-standardized coefficient is 0.940, with a highly significant P-value (***), standard error (S.E.) is 0.034, critical ratio (C.R.) is 20.038, and the standardized coefficient is 0.887, indicating that volunteer recruitment has a significant positive impact on satisfaction.

This is consistent with the analysis by Wang (2020) in "Study on Volunteer Satisfaction of 2019 Zhengkai International Marathon", which pointed out that the satisfaction of recruitment and selection had a significant positive impact on the overall satisfaction of volunteers.

5.2.6 The marathon volunteer training factors positively affect the volunteer satisfaction

It is found that in the path analysis of volunteer training to satisfaction, the non-standardized coefficient of satisfaction is 0.944, the standard error (S.E.) is 0.033, and the critical ratio (C.R.) is 28.322.

The corresponding standardization coefficient is 0.911, indicating that volunteer training has a significant positive effect on satisfaction (MYD). Li (2022) verified relevant studies that strengthening skills and knowledge training help improve nurses' satisfaction and work ability.

Liu (2017) considered volunteer training is the need for volunteers to realize their self-worth. Reasonable training is an important aspect that improve volunteer satisfaction.

5.2.7 The position arrangement of marathon volunteers' factors positively affect the volunteer satisfaction

In the path of position arrangement to satisfaction, the non-standardized coefficient is 0.954, and the P-value (***) indicates that this path is statistically significant. The corresponding standardization coefficient was 0.948, indicating that volunteer satisfaction (MYD) was significantly positively affected by volunteer position arrangement. To verify relevant studies, Hu (2021) in the allocation of volunteer service posts, their abilities match the post needs, it can improve the work efficiency and satisfaction of volunteers.

5.2.8 The assessment and Incentive of marathon volunteers' factors positively affect the volunteer satisfaction

It is found that for the incentive path of evaluation of volunteer satisfaction, the non-standardized coefficient is 0.937, with highly significant P-value (***), standard error (S.E.) is 0.033, critical ratio (C.R.) is 28.028, and standardization coefficient is 0.944. The results show that the evaluation motivation of volunteers has a significant positive impact on satisfaction.

Zhou (2022) proposed that subjective evaluation and motivation can further improve the quality and efficiency of college students' volunteer service in the new era. Liu (2014) in the volunteer activities of sports events, volunteers can have a strong sense of identity, so that they will be more enthusiastic in the future work.

5.2.9 Volunteer satisfaction positively affects volunteer management model

In the path from volunteer satisfaction to volunteer management model, the non-standardized coefficient was 0.961, the standard error was 0.024, the critical ratio was 40.274, and the significance level was ***.

The standardization coefficient was 0.980, which revealed the significant positive impact of volunteer satisfaction on volunteer management model. The incentive justice theory proposed by American psychologist Adams (1965), job satisfaction affects the enthusiasm and efficiency of work. Zhao (2016) discussed the job satisfaction of medical workers plays an important role in improving management work efficiency.

5.2.10 Volunteer satisfaction plays an intermediary role factors positively affect between volunteer recruitment and volunteer management model

In the mediation effect path coefficient analysis, the mediating effect of volunteer satisfaction on volunteer management model through volunteer recruitment is 0.034, the standard error of the intermediate effect is 0.02, and the 95% confidence interval is 0.004 to 0.083, excluding 0. It shows that the mediating effect of satisfaction between volunteer recruitment and volunteer management model is significant.

This supports the research of some scholars, such as Zhou (2023), that there is a partial intermediate effect between job identity and job performance, and the intermediate effect accounts for 28.1% of the total effect value. These results suggest that preschool teachers' job

satisfaction plays an important role in the influence of professional identity on job performance.

5.2.11 Volunteer satisfaction plays an intermediary role factors positively affect between volunteer training and volunteer management model

In the mediation effect path coefficient analysis, the mediating effect value of volunteer training on volunteer management model through volunteer satisfaction is 0.032, the standard error of the intermediate effect is 0.018, and the 95% confidence interval is 0.005 to 0.076, excluding 0. The direct impact of volunteer training on volunteer management model is 0.177, and the total impact after taking into account the mediation effect is 0.209, both of which are significant at the level of 0.01, indicating that the mediation effect between volunteer training and volunteer management model is significant.

Zhu (2023) studied the internal relationship between teacher training, job satisfaction and organizational commitment, and found that teacher training can significantly positively predict organizational commitment, and job satisfaction plays a complete mediating role in the influence path of the two. The conclusions are consistent.

5.2.12 Volunteer satisfaction plays an intermediary role factors positively affect between volunteer position arrangement and volunteer management model

The mediating effect of volunteer position arrangement on volunteer management model through volunteer satisfaction is 0.038, the standard error of the intermediate effect is 0.021, and the 95% confidence interval is 0.005 to 0.085, excluding 0. The mediating effect between volunteer's job arrangement and volunteer management model is significant. At the same time, it also validates some previous research conclusions.

Chang (2010) believes that under the premise of person-post matching, the improvement of job satisfaction will help produce higher job performance. Chen (2018) proposed that job satisfaction plays a completely mediating role among job matching and job performance. The improvement of job satisfaction contributes to higher job performance.

5.2.13 Volunteer satisfaction plays an intermediary role factors positively affect between volunteer assessment and Incentive and volunteer management model

In the mediation effect path coefficient analysis, the mediation effect value of volunteer assessment incentive on volunteer management model through volunteer satisfaction is 0.033. The standard error for intermediate effect is 0.017 and the 95% confidence interval is 0.005 to 0.072, excluding 0.

The results show that there is a significant mediating effect between volunteers' assessment motivation and volunteer management model, which verifies the mediating effect of satisfaction. In line with relevant research views, Li (2023) suggests that enhancing the intrinsic motivation of primary health workers can not only directly improve their work performance, but also indirectly improve their performance through improving job satisfaction.

5.3 Suggestion

This study confirmed all the research hypotheses, revealed the internal mechanism between the influencing factors of marathon volunteer management and volunteer satisfaction and volunteer management model, and provided a new theoretical perspective for the study of marathon volunteer management. It has certain theoretical contributions and innovations, but there are certain research limitations. In this paper, volunteer satisfaction is only used as the mediating variable. Other mediating variables or even moderating variables can be explored in the future, and different variables often lead to different conclusions. Further research is needed in the future.

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